

under greenhouse conditions. Individually caged test plants were infested with newly hatched 1st-instar larvae from a *M. patnalis* greenhouse colony.

M. patnalis survived on four of the

weed species. Survival was highest (48%) on *Leersia hexandra*, with a 17-d larval period. *Echinochloa colona* leaves were scraped, but the larvae did not live to pupate. Survival was poor and larval

period extended (25 d) on *Cyperus difformis*, which may cause the larvae to migrate to the young transplanted rice crop early in the growing season. □

Rice whorl maggot (RWM) effect on yield loss

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RWM usually attacks irrigated rice plants and retards their growth from seedbed stage to about 40 d after transplanting (DT). In hot, lowland conditions in the Philippines, plants usually recover from RWM damage, and exhibit no yield loss even with heavy infestation. However, scientists suspect there has been some yield loss from RWM in the IRRI maximum yield trials (MYT). We evaluated the effect of RWM damage with 2 insecticide treatments on 10 cultivars or lines planted in the MYT (Table 1) in Mar-Jul 1984.

RWM damage ranged from 1.8 to 6.5% in the insecticide-treated plots and 11.4 to

43.5% in check plots (Table 2). The correlation coefficient between RWM damage and yield loss was 0.57 ($n = 10$) and not significant, indicating that RWM infestation at the levels in this study did not affect yield.

Similarly, percent deadhearts caused by stem borers in early stages did not significantly correlate with yield loss ($r = 0.02$). In contrast, percent of tungro-infected plants was highly correlated with yield loss ($r = 0.98^{**}$). □

Table 1. Insecticide treatments.

Wk after transplanting	Highly protected	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Check	Rate (kg ai/ha)
1	Diazinon 5G and monocrotophos	1.0 + 1.5		
2	Deltamethrin 2.5EC	0.0125		
3	Diazinon 5G and carbaryl 85WP	1.0 + 1.5		
4	Acephate 75SP	0.75		
5	MIPC 50WP	0.75		
6	Monocrotophos 30EC	0.75	Monocrotophos 30EC	0.75
7	Acephate 75SP	0.75	Acephate 75SP	0.75
8	Diazinon 20EC	0.75	Diazinon 20EC	0.75
11	Acephate 75SP	0.75	Acephate 75SP	0.75

Table 2. Effect of RWM infestation on the yield of 10 rice varieties and lines used in the IRRI MYT.^a

Cultivar/line	RWM damaged leaves (%) on 20 hills/plot		Deadhearts (%) on 160 hills/plot		Hills (%) with tungro virus disease on 160 hills/plot, 40 DT ^d		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Highly protected ^b	Check ^c	Highly protected	Check	Highly protected	Check	Highly protected	Check
IR5 8	3.40 bcd	18.82 abc	1.14 bc	0.56 ab	0.00 a	0.00 a	3.73 b	3.38 b
IR31847-67-2-1-1-2	2.65 bc	29.75 c	1.38 bc	0.64 ab	0.00 a	0.00 a	4.36 b	4.50 c
IR36	2.64 abcd	27.39 c	2.66 d	0.38 ab	2.03 a	42.65 b	4.20 b	2.20 ab
IE29725-3-1-3-2	3.10 bcd	27.39 c	1.28 bc	0.52 ab	0.00 a	0.00 a	3.78 b	4.10 c
IR31851-6-3-3-3-2	4.09 cd	15.22 ab	0.47 a	0.43 ab	0.16 a	0.00 a	4.53 b	4.26 c
IR8	6.48 d	40.52 cd	0.00 a	0.00 a	100.00 c	97.50 c	0.00 a	0.00 a
IR42	3.31 bcd	43.58 d	0.64 ab	0.00 a	13.03 b	93.75 c	3.45 b	0.00 a
IR21840-154-3-2-2-3	1.81 a	11.43 a	1.34 bc	0.64 ab	0.00 a	0.00 a	3.41 b	3.85 c
IR29723-143-3-2-1	1.89 b	25.08 c	1.67 cd	0.91 b	0.00 a	0.00 a	4.51 b	4.97 abcd
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	3.00 bc	21.06 bc	1.20 bc	1.16 b	0.00 a	0.00 a	3.61 b	3.37 b

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bHighly protected from 1 wk to 11 wk after transplanting. ^cProtected only after 6 wk to 11 wk after transplanting. ^dDays after transplanting.

Sensitivity levels of green leafhopper (GLH) populations to insecticides at IRRI in 1983-84

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We suspected that GLH at IRRI were

becoming less sensitive or resistant to insecticides because of frequent application. GLH were collected from tungro-infected IR22 in Dec 1983 and reared on TN1 in the greenhouse. Insecticide sensitivity of the F₂ GLH populations was compared to that of a greenhouse culture that had not been exposed to insecticide treatments. We

used a Burkard microapplicator to apply 0.2 µl each of 5 insecticides, diluted by acetone, on CO₂ anaesthetized 2- to 5-d-old GLH adults.

The LD₅₀ values of the greenhouse population ranged from 0.99 to 8.23; that of field-collected GLH was from 2.40 to 26.47. The estimated resistance ratio

Comparison of insecticide reaction of greenhouse and F₂ populations of field-collected GLH, IRRI, Feb 1984.

Insecticide	LD ₅₀ ^a (μg/g 24 h)		Difference (F-GH)	ERR ^c
	Field-collected population (F)	Greenhouse population (GH)		
BPMC	5.11	2.86	2.25 ns	1.79
Carbaryl	7.01	4.40	2.61 ns	1.59
Carbofuran	2.40	0.99	1.41 ns	2.42
Diazinon	26.41	8.23	18.24*	3.22
Monocrotophos	9.16	6.25	2.91 ns	1.47

^a Av of 3 replications (20 adult females/replication). ^b* = significant at 5%, ns = not significant.

^c Estimated resistance ratio = $\frac{LD_{50} \text{ value for F}}{LD_{50} \text{ value for GH}}$.

was from 1.47 to 3.22. This indicates that the field-collected GLH may be developing resistance to the tested insecticides. Only the diazinon-treated field-collected population was significantly more resistant than the greenhouse culture (see table). □

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Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Alternate foods of bandicoot rats in deep water rice areas of Bangladesh

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While conducting rodent control experiments in deep water rice areas of Tangail district in 1983, we found that rats ate snails, water lily fruit, and water hyacinth stems. In early 1984, we visited the same area to record rodent damage to boro rice. There were many bandicoot rat burrows near the dike of the boro rice field, but there was little rodent damage. To determine what the rats were eating, we excavated a burrow system (see figure) and found 68 modified stems of *Nymphaea lotus* (715 g) and 32 snail shells (*Pila globosa* and *Viviparus bengalensis*) in the food chamber. In laboratory tests we found that bandicoot rats can easily live on *P. globosa* and tubers of *N. lotus* (see table). Farmers often use the tubers of *N. lotus* as food during crisis, and 1 kg costs about \$0.25 during the season. Snails are fed to ducks. We also found eight rat litters in the same burrow system. □

Bandicoot rat burrow system in a dike during boro season in a deep water rice are in Bangladesh.

Body weight increase of *Bandicota indica* after 5 d feeding on snails and tubers. Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, 1984.

Food ^a	Amount consumed (g/d)			Body weight (g)		Increase (%)
	Min	Max	Mean	Prefeeding	Postfeeding	
Snail	28.0	96.0	61.8	442.0	451.0	2
Tuber	37.0	49.0	42.2			
Snail	0.0	80.0	34.6	287.0	287.0	0
Tuber	5.0	37.0	26.2			
Snail	31.0	90.0	64.0	242.0	277.0	14
Tuber	45.0	69.0	56.8			

^a Snail = *Pila globosa*, tuber = modified stems of *Nymphaea lotus*.

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